

What is information governance?

Context: Pre reading for the UK TRE – Information Governance Interest Group joint session

More information about the event:

https://www.uktre.org/en/latest/events/wg_workshops/2025-03-26-march-meeting

Date: 26th March 09:30-13:00

Authors: Prepared by the Information Governance (IG) Interest Group

Introduction:

This document holds five different initiating thoughts in the pages that follow.

These are designed to provoke a discussion at the event, and to also help educate on what information Governance is / could be.

Contents

View 1: Information Governance is...	2
View 2: Information Governance is...	3
View 3: Information Governance is...	4
View 4: Information Governance is...	5
View 5: Information Governance is...	6

View 1: Information Governance is...

IG is about	Maximising the public benefit from the use of confidential data resources, whilst managing risks to individuals and society appropriately
IG covers	<p>The five safes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The purpose of any data use: identifying public benefit and potential risks, users and uses, archiving, reproducibility and ethics • Data management systems • Disclosure control of input and outputs, for quantitative and qualitative data • The skills of people handling the data and making decisions
Good IG is	<p>Outcome focused:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effective – achieving valuable goals • Efficient – achieving goals with minimal resources • Safe – achieving goals while protecting the confidentiality of individuals
IG decisions should be	<p>EDRU:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evidence-based (ie not hypotheticals) • Default open (ie “do unless we can’t” , not “don’t do unless we can”) • Risk-managed (everything has risk; risk is balanced with benefits) • User-centred (where do you want to be? Start there and work backwards)

View 2: Information Governance is...

Information Governance is the main protection against risks including:

1. Staff/researchers breaking the law – jail/hefty fines.
2. Data breaches – compromising patient safety, protecting IP
3. Reputational risks – data controllers & data users
4. Bad research – e.g. unethical, insecure, inconsistent
5. Research not happening – balancing needs of researcher & representing and informing controllers, reassurance.
6. “That’s not what we agreed”

- Through:
 - accountability, & making sure everyone knows their responsibilities (data sharing agreements, user agreements etc)
 - audit (this is what we did and why),
 - risk management & explanation – operationalising the Five Safes,
 - training everything that isn't technical/user service – except the things that are.
- Keeping researchers, staff and data subjects safe.

View 3: Information Governance is...

Simply: It's the legal and ethical framework that governs the information, it's the security and access controls that protect the information and it's the process by which risks around deviations or breaches of that information are identified and managed. Information governance should be *transparent* and *clear* for those who manage data and those who access it.

Legal and ethics:

- Ensures that the information is handled in accordance with applicable laws and the ethical provisioning and use of the data
- Data management and how it should be created, stored, and managed, including archiving and deletion

Security and access controls:

- Protects information from unauthorised access and/or data breaches

Risk management:

- Proactively identifying risks around legal/ethical compliance, security and access, and mitigating those risks through technical and/or process controls.

View 4: Information Governance is...

View 5: Information Governance is...

Input to the UK TRE Info Governance event on 26th March 2025

Pete Barnsley, 11/02/2025 (original version 22/01/2025)

The Francis Crick Institute; co-chair IG Interest Group; co-chair UK TRE community.

Well, it is governing information isn't it!

The primary purpose of information Governance (IG) is not complying with the law around data, that is the responsibility of every legal entity, their employees, and citizens. IG is a role to minimise the time it takes for an approved, funded, ethical project to start using the data for the project's purpose. In addition, a secondary key role of Information Governance is to get the most out of the data that the legal entity is being paid to maintain. This is will be done 'safely'.

"Information Governance" could mean many different things, and does, to many people. Figure 1 is an attempt to formalise the scope of Information Governance, via objects with defined type and meaning (see key). The aim is to gain critique and challenge to test this proposed "hypothesis" and so improve and complete it.

Figure 1 shows a legal entity (to the right of the vertical line on the left separating external relevant things). The IG scope activities are in the centre, with other relevant 'technical' activities slightly greyed out and separated to the right of the wavy line; these things represent responsibilities owned by other areas and not IG. To have IG responsibilities the Entity by definition has to hold data that demands such IG activity with agreed datasets registered into a catalogue and recording those data processing agreements (things in the bottom left corner of Figure 1).

Figure 1: Model scoping Information Governance activities, accountability and boundaries

There are three main processes that IG covers:

The first process is the development of data sharing agreements (DSA) to document the interactions between collaborating partners as they complete 'research' projects doing new things with data. In completing the DSA template, DPIAs, Policies and accreditation

requirements will be developed or called, and these details written into records / registries. (this linkage from DSA to registry is shown by the overlap and grey background block).

The second process is the orchestration (control of deployment and configuration management) of approved / agreed Users, Organisations, Facilities, their users, and Permissions. All these decisions are held in registries (and these are shared by other ‘technical’ activities to implement the agreed model). The registries shown on the dividing wavy line in Figure 1, define the settings (facilities and users of them); the users and researchers; the research organisations (RPOs) they work for; the projects these parties have signed agreements for; and the permissions to rows of data allowed to complete the project’s work. Part of the end outcome of process 1 and 2 is therefore the shape of the *safes* that fit that project and define how the project will operate in the ‘technical’ area. These shapes are few in number and ‘standard’, suited to the specific types of data processing activities needed.

The third process is the audit and accreditation of data sharing infrastructures; both applying for and maintaining accreditations for the Legal Entities activities, but also those of suppliers involved downstream in enabling the ‘technical’ activities – such as cloud providers and platform services – (indicated by the arrow extending into that area of Figure 1). This process activity also includes supporting audit and compliance activities for the external ‘up stream’ parties such as the “data owning” data controllers, ICO etc. Where possible public visibility of such audit helps the social contract and reinforces trustworthiness.

Because there are a number of legal agreements involved: with service providers supporting the ‘technical’ activities; with data ‘sharing’ parties; with data ‘owning’ parties; risk has become a primary currency. It is important to acknowledge this, and work to cut through to a model where uncertainty has been removed. Although there is wide diversity in the projects (by definition and design) there is not such diversity in the mitigation ‘safe’ solutions. Common and aligned processes, using open and national registries can enable trust in, and belief of, secure data processing. This reinforcement can help to sustain and strength the public societal contract in using personal data for public good.

Whilst Information Governance is definable and its practical activities can be aligned between organisations (e.g Figure 1), it also has wide diversity in the resulting shape driven by local context and culture. Each implementation tries to balance (dynamically) a set of in-tension dimensions:

- innovation and regulation
- individual rights and public benefit
- transparency and nondisclosure
- security and collaboration.

All these “tensions” are supported by the framework in Figure 1.

By expanding out the three processes flows, developing glossary definitions for the registries (and semantic meaning for what they do and do not do); and modelling the ‘safe’ patterns; we can allow the diversity of research purposes to be supported on common data platforms running on common infrastructure platforms. And the Information Governance models in use can (and must) be federated!